

THE CONCEPT OF TOLERANCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

Object of research: Pedagogical conditions for the development of tolerance in extracurricular activities of students of pedagogical colleges. Allowed to create. It is necessary to develop collaborative skills, to harmonize different perspectives, to be self-directed in a particular situation. The urgency of the problem of promoting tolerance among students of teacher training colleges, as the spiritual recovery of modern Ukrainian society depends on future teachers. Main scientific results: According to the results of the seminar "To increase the tolerance of future teachers", the vast majority of mentors of student groups found a high level of readiness to cultivate tolerance among students of teacher training colleges (75.0 %).

For example, conducting a training lesson "What is tolerance?" aimed: to bring students closer to a deeper understanding of the "tolerance" phenomenon; contribute to improving student relationships on the principles of tolerance. Such forms as discussions turned out to be effective "Why is it difficult to be tolerant in our life?", "Yes and no", etc. Classes with training elements "What is tolerance?", "Life tree", "Seven areas of tolerance training", project activities, video presentations, dramas, the solution of problem situations and the use of reflective, empathic, dialogical techniques and the like. The field of practical use of the research results: Attracting students of pedagogical colleges to such activities as: research, artistic and aesthetic, value-oriented, organizational and managerial allowed creating the conditions necessary for developing

cooperation skills, harmonizing different views, self-orientation in that or other situation.

Introduction

In this article, no answers to these broad questions are given, but, drawing from findings from an ethnographic study, concepts that can be helpful in analyzing such questions are suggested. The focus is on students' informal relations at school, especially on situations in which tolerance and understanding are challenged and differences constructed. Enactments of bullying and sex-based and racist harassment are such situations. The context is the 1st year of the Finnish secondary school when students are about 13 years old. Observations from everyday life in school are reflected upon in relation to the perceptions of the students and to their school memories at the age of about

18, as well as in relation to their teachers' perceptions. The article draws on interlinked studies. Firstly, data and analyses of a collective, comparative, and cross cultural ethnographic research project in two secondary schools in Helsinki are used. Secondly, in an ethnographically grounded longitudinal life-history study, Tracing Transitions – Follow-up Study of Post-sixteen Students, Tuula Gordon and I reinterview the same young men and women that participated in the earlier study. We analyze economic, cultural, and biographical as well as educational aspects in the paths pursued by young people. In the interviews, our interviewees also reflect on their memories concerning life in secondary. In the methodological approach of both studies, we have tried to grasp multiple and sometimes contradictory processes and practices in school, but also meanings that the participants have given to these – their instant reflections, when still at school, as well as reflections as remembered. Our approach is influenced by, who advise school ethnographers to become “promiscuous bricoleurs, selecting whatever techniques, theories, or insights can be best deployed in any particular project”. They urge ethnographers to take an eclectic and pragmatic approach to research, and not view methods, disciplines, and schools of thought as “sectarian doctrines with iron barriers between them.” In developing the conceptual and theoretical framework, we have drawn freely on a range of theoretical perspectives, including social constructionist, cultural, materialist, post structural, and feminist theory. In this article I use concepts that have used in a review article. They differentiate between “equity problematic” studies and

“knowledge problematic” studies. Whilst the “equity problematic” study examines questions of representation and access of individuals and groups to educational and social practices, the “knowledge problematic” study focuses on the systems of reason that are embodied in educational policy. Knowledge as a dimension of power is central here, and under consideration the “qualities” that differentiate the possibilities of individuals for action and participation. When the perspective is that of “knowledge problematic,” it is not race, gender, or class itself that is the central concern of research, but the focus is on analyzing how these are constructed in educational contexts, and how the subjectivities are produced by normalizing certain characteristics and capabilities of the individual, thus producing difference. Popkewitz and Lindblad talk about the production of “race-ness,” “gender-ness,” or “class-ness” of individuality. I paraphrase them, and use the term “different-ness” in order to pay attention to situations in which diversities and differences of young people occur to be frozen into categories or labels that are used as a basis for bullying and racist or sex-based harassment. The psychological analysis of tolerance in a teacher’s pedagogical activity testifies to the fact that it is an important professional property of a teacher. The essence of the basic concepts and the angle of mentality were revealed, the peculiarities of teachers' tolerance were analyzed in the educational process, the skills and qualifications of teachers of pedagogical and physiological sciences in higher education were very thorough. Pedagogical practice plays a major role in shaping a teacher’s professional qualifications. In the process of pedagogical practice, the student's pedagogical skills

and qualifications are quickly formed. His ability to study the development of creative and pedagogical phenomena, the basics of pedagogical skills are determined. Pedagogical practice has a special place in the system of teacher training. It is an integral part of the educational process at the university and provides an integral part of the theoretical training and practical work of future teachers. In the process of pedagogical practice the following tasks are solved: - to cultivate in students interest and love for the teaching profession; - Promotion and approval of the process of using psycho-pedagogical and special knowledge in solving specific pedagogical tasks. Teachers play an important role in the lives of the students they face. They influence what and how students learn in the classroom each day, and encouraging and nurturing them helps students do what they can and achieve their goals. But their impact goes beyond what we see in everyday interactions within school walls. Effective teachers have the opportunity to contribute beyond the classroom and school day. Teachers can demonstrate outside the classroom that they have invested in student life and community. In addition to their responsibility to educate students, teachers play an important role in developing character or shaping a student's reputation, honor, and integrity. When they build relationships with students through participation in sports games, student productions, and other things, teachers take care of their students outside of class and success in the classroom. The purpose of this chapter is to present the key concepts and actors in pedagogy and didactics in the context of institutional teaching. We present a holistic approach to education and view human beings as

lifelong learners who need to be educated comprehensively to actualize their full potential. In this chapter we discuss how pedagogy, the science and art of teaching, can promote the educational goals identified in the curriculum. In this chapter we adhere to the Didaktik curriculum tradition in which values and morals are emphasized in guiding the teaching-studying-learning process. This means that pedagogy is moral in nature, and the teacher's main task is to reflect the values underlying her teaching and the purposes she wants to advance in her teaching. We also discuss the current pedagogical challenges in both basic and higher education in educating students for the twenty-first century. The purpose of this chapter is to present the basic concepts and actors of pedagogical relations in the context of pedagogy and educational institutions. The objectives of education are set out in the national curriculum and in more detailed institutional curricula. In many countries, such as Finland, the goal of education is to support the development of the whole individual, not just the cognitive field. In this holistic approach, people are lifelong learners and need to be educated in all areas of education in order to reach their full potential. These domains cover three areas of learning identified by Benjamin Bloom: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Many learning tasks, such as ethical skills, require teaching and learning in both cognitive and affective areas. In this chapter, we discuss how pedagogy, science, and the art of teaching can promote the learning goals set out in the curriculum. We can identify two different curriculum tradition influencing national curriculums in different countries. The Bildung tradition aims at educating individuals to become competent citizens

who actualize their individual talents and also benefit the society with their competences . Bildung advocates the importance of individual and society transformation through education. In Europe and Nordic countries, Didaktik is a curriculum tradition guided by the philosophy of Bildung and the idea of educating instruction, *erziehende Unterricht*, in educational institutions. In that tradition, the pedagogical relation between the teacher and students, the content relation of a teacher to the subject matter and the didactic relation of a teacher to students' learning are seen as core elements in teaching-studying-learning process. In this chapter, we adhere to the Didaktik curriculum tradition in which values and morals are emphasized in guiding the teaching-studying-learning process and in educating pupils as whole. This means that pedagogy is moral in nature, and the teacher's main task is to reflect the values underlying her teaching and the purposes she wants to advance in her teaching. In addition to the values established in the national curriculum, the teacher needs to be aware of the ethical codes guiding the teaching profession. The professional status of teachers differs from country to country. In Finland, for example, teachers are considered ethical professionals who can be trusted and who share similar basic values about their work. These values are established in the ethical codes for teachers, which were first published in Finland in 1998. The values are dignity, truthfulness, fairness, responsibility and freedom . In 2017 the Teachers' Union in Finland continued to strengthen the professional status of its members and established the Comenius' Oath for teachers .The purpose of this oath was to support teachers and provide a

concrete reminder of the ethical foundation of their profession. The freedom given to teachers challenges them constantly to develop their ethical skills with regard to their students, colleagues, themselves and the networks with which they cooperate. In this pedagogical challenge, teachers need ethical sensitivity to identify and solve context-specific moral dilemmas in teaching .In Anglo-American traditions, Shulman's range of teacher practical knowledge, and in particular pedagogical content knowledge, informed and guided research practices related to teacher and teacher education. He suggests that teacher training programs combine two knowledge bases to train teachers more effectively. These two knowledge bases are content and pedagogy. A crucial aspect of developing teachers 'knowledge of teaching their subject is knowledge on the subject. The second aspect of teacher knowledge is pedagogical knowledge, which, in addition to knowing the topic on its own, shifts to the scope of the topic to be taught. Pedagogical meaningful knowledge can be called a combination of meaningful knowledge and pedagogical knowledge; this allows teachers to support students 'learning, organize pedagogically meaningful teaching, and select appropriate teaching and assessment methods in teaching the topic. Pedagogical knowledge is unique to teachers, for example, it distinguishes a science teacher from a scientist. With this knowledge, a teacher can teach a variety of students a particular context effectively and with unique characteristics, which helps him or her to understand the content personally. The article raises the problem of education of tolerance in students as a social and pedagogical phenomenon and stresses the importance and urgency of this problem at

the present stage of society development. The author examines the theoretical basis and the possibility of development of tolerant relations in vocational education as a special value of human rights, which states respect for the opinions of others, to various forms of self-expression and human individuality. The definition of «tolerance» offers diversified understanding of the content and the value of this characteristic. The study of the theoretical sources allowed the authors to outline the objectives and activities to promote tolerance. Solutions for selected tasks considered arsenal of interactive approaches in educational work. Analysis of the available resources and opportunities of higher education has led the authors to the idea of independent structural unit in the structure of university that encourages tolerance, high morality, which would be, according to the authors, the quality indicators of education. The article focuses on the qualities of a true teacher that the teacher should nurture and possess and help to improve pedagogical skills. The growing role of the university teacher and the need to further improve the pedagogical skills of the university teaching staff stems from the general speech of the society aimed at strengthening the principles of humanity in human relations, civil society and the ideology of humanity. The article details

the principles that guide, support, and update teachers in educating their students.

In conclusion , theatrical art is an effective means of educating a high school student, as it is during this period that the personal formation of the adolescent takes place. The young spectator (student) sits in the auditorium and takes an active part in the theatrical action in the process of understanding the performance. The theater has an educational value, and it is important for the teacher not only to watch the play with the students, but also to discuss with them what they have seen and experienced. A visit to the theater shapes not only the culture of the audience, but also personal qualities, spiritual and moral values, self-awareness, including tolerance. Realizing the potential of theater culture, various theatrical techniques and technologies are used in schools. In particular, theatrical pedagogy suggests the use of play techniques in the educational process, as play is a universal form of human activity, a means by which students learn the reality that surrounds them that changes during play activities. Play activities in the learning process are aimed at shaping the personality of students, revealing their creative potential, developing imagination. Through play, the child socializes.

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